

Assessment of Heavy Metal Contamination and Potential Ecological Risk in Crude Oil Exploitation Sites in Mmahu, Imo State

Eches E. E.^{1&2} Nwawuike I. M.*² Onyeaunforo C. C.²

¹Department of Agricultural Education, Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

²Department of Soil Science and Environment, Imo State University Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: nobleify200@gmail.com

Received: February 13, 2025; Accepted: April 7, 2025; Published: May 15, 2025

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15421746>

Abstract: This study sought to investigate the concentrations of some selected heavy metals and their ecotoxicological risks in crude oil impacted soils in Mmahu, Imo State. The soil samples were randomly collected from five crude oil exploitation sites at the depth of 0 - 15 cm using soil auger. In each site, five soil samples soils were collected given a total of 25 soil samples. The samples were air-dried and sieved to remove root debris. The selected heavy metals and soil properties were analyzed using standard laboratory procedures. The results obtained were subjected to analysis of variance and correlation analysis. The sampled soils were low in %clay and %silt but high in sand fraction. The pH ranged from moderate to slightly acidic while the soil organic matter (SOM) was from medium to high. The results of the heavy metal from the soils showed that all the analyzed heavy metals were detected though As, Cr, Ni, and Fe were lower than their permissible limits except for Cd according to WHO/FAO. The interrelationship among soil properties and heavy metals in the soil showed that soil properties influenced heavy metal availability. The interrelationship between Fe and heavy metals showed that in some of the heavy metal presence were geogenic while in others were anthropogenic. The results of CF and C_d indicated that As, Cr, Ni and Fe were low to moderately contaminated while Cd was found to be very high. The PI values of Cr, As and Ni indicate they are unpolluted while that of Cd is polluted. PCI analysis found that Cd across sites were very severe while concentrations of As, Cr, Ni and Fe ranged from low to moderate severe. The concentrations of As, Cr, Ni and Fe in the exploitation sites pose little or no ecological risk. However, the Potential Ecological Risk Factor (Er^i) concentrations of Cd in different sites in the study area at $Er^i \geq 320$ poses a very high potential ecological risk while values of Potential Ecological Risk Index (RI) recorded across sites were ≥ 600 and a indicates a very high ecological risk in Mmahu.

Keywords: Heavy metal, contamination, Potential ecological risk, Crude oil, Mmahu, Exploitation sites,

Introduction

A heavy metal is any metallic chemical element whose density is relatively high and at low concentration, it is considered toxic. Heavy metals cannot be destroyed or degraded and they occur naturally in the earth's crust. According to Nemati et al. (2011) and Chinedu and Chukwuemeka (2018), heavy metals are toxic pollutants which have the capacity to persist in the environment and degrade ecological quality (Defew et al., 2005). Examples of heavy metals associated with crude oil pollution include; cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), arsenic (As), chromium (Cr), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), mercury (Hg), nickel (Ni) and iron (Fe) among others (Nriagu et al., 2016). These heavy metals however, can be transferred through trophic processes in both terrestrial and aquatic environment and as such, possess substantial ecotoxicological risks (Mallick et al., 2019; Proshad et al., 2019). Not only does these heavy metals distort ecological balance in crude oil polluted soils, they also endanger living organisms there (Lu et al., 2012).

Oil and gas is the bedrock of the Nigerian economy. However, the production process of oil and gas contributes greatly to environmental pollution. Thus, Kadafa (2012) opines

that crude oil production and distribution approach in Nigeria is fraught with pollution. Also, wastes associated with petroleum production are often laden with heavy metals and could possibly lead to soil contamination (Oyinlola and Adebayo, 2014). Due to crude oil activities relating to exploitation, processing and transportation, Ohaji/Egbema has witnessed several cases of oil related pollution which has resulted in varying scales of environmental degradation (Nwawuike et al., 2023).

The exploration, discovery and exploitation of vast deposits of petroleum resources within Niger Delta, to which Ohaji/Egbema is a part of, began in the 1950s. This venture has drastically exposed the Niger Delta region to various scales of crude oil related pollution (Okoye et al., 2021; Orisakwe, 2021). It is pertinent to note that according to Niger Delta is one of the ten most important wetland and marine ecosystems in the world. However, the Niger Delta is ranked among the five very severely degraded ecosystems in the world due to the unsustainable crude oil production approach (Kadafa, 2012). According to Nwadiogbu et al. (2024), cases of environmental pollution due to

petroleum related activities in the Niger Delta has been associated with regular oil spills, particularly through rupture of pipelines, oil wells blow outs, bunkering, tanker accidents and sabotage. The environmental degradation due to such incidences affects soil, air and water bodies.

There are several cases of pollution due to oil production and related activities in Niger Delta. For instance, UNDP (2006) holds that between 1976 to 2001, not less than 6,817 oil spills occurred in Nigeria with a loss of approximately three million barrels of oil out of which nearly 70% of the spilled oil was lost to the environment. Again, an oil spillage at Shell's Bonga Oil Field which occurred in 2011 released about 40,000 barrels into the surrounding environment and it negatively impacted on not less than 350 farming communities (Alozie, 2020). The spills ravaging the oil producing communities in Niger Delta equally affected oil producing communities in Ohaji/Egbema. Report by Ihiegbulem (2011) indicated that on June 18, 2004, oil spillage occurred in Umuogwa, Umuodebi and Awarra communities in Ohaji/Egbema. This led to the degradation of both terrestrial and aquatic lives. Similarly, according to Amobi (2017) Abacheke, Ugada and

Etwkuru communities in Ohaji/Egbema witnessed oil spillage that devastated farmlands. Recently, on April 22, 2022, an explosion at a bunkering site at Abaezi in Ohaji/Egbema led to the death of some people, properties were destroyed by the ensuing inferno and environment degraded.

Though all the soils with Mmahu crude oil exploitation site may not have been impacted directly by oil spillages, gas flaring or explosions; however, there is the likelihood that many soils within the area might have been indirectly affected through redistribution by over-land flow and acid rain. Hence, Njoku et al. (2014) submits that no fewer than 60% of the people in Ohaji/Egbema who depend on land resources in the area for their livelihood have been exposed to varying scales of oil related pollution directly or indirectly.

It is therefore critical to evaluate the impact of crude oil pollution near the exploitation sites in Mmahu to ascertain the extent of soil contamination and risk posed to the ecology of the area. Therefore, this study seeks to assess the metal contamination and potential ecological risk in crude oil exploitation sites in Mmahu, Imo State.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Mmahu is an oil producing community and the headquarters of Ohaji/Egbema local government area of Imo State. Other economic activities associated with Mmahu besides oil production include; production of such crops likes cassava, yam, maize, palm oil processing, hunting and fishing among others (Okorie et al., 2020). The study area lies within the tropical rainforest zone. The rainy season starts around April and lasts till October while the dry season extends between November and

March (Nwawuike et al., 2023). According to NIMET (2014), the annual precipitation on average is in excess of 2,500 mm while temperatures are in the range of between 26°C to 30°C. The topography of the study area is low-lying and generally within 80 meters above sea level. The soils of Ohaji/Egbema are geologically derived from the Benin Formation (Ahukaemere et al., 2016). Mmahu is located in the northern part of Ohaji/Egbema and lies approximately between latitudes (5.525794 to 5.525985N) and longitudes (6.751645 to 6.752313E) (Fig.1)

Figure 1 Map showing study location (Source:This study)

Contaminated Soil Sample Collection

Five (5) crude oil contaminated soil samples each were obtained from 5 different locations at crude oil exploitation sites in Mmahu, Ohaji/Egbema. The soil samples were randomly collected within 1 - 3 meters away from the exploitation sites. Thus, a total of twenty-five (25) crude oil polluted soil samples were used for this study. The crude oil polluted soil samples were collected at a depth ranging from 0 - 15 cm using a Combination Edelman Soil Auger.

Sample Handling and Preparation

The collected crude oil polluted soil samples were packaged in plastic bags and labeled in the field. The samples were air dried for 120 hours to reduce moisture content and then repackaged in zip-lock bags, labeled and carefully packed in plastic boxes before sending it for laboratory analysis.

Laboratory Analysis

The collected crude oil polluted soil samples were analyzed for heavy metal concentrations and soil properties (pH, organic matter and particle size distribution). The heavy metals analyzed for were; arsenic, nickel, chromium, cadmium and iron. The choice of these metals is because they are associated

with petroleum pollution. The selected metals were extracted using wet acid digestion method and the filtrates were analyzed using standard Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) procedures. The pH was measured in both water and KCl solution using glass electrode coupled pH meter. Organic matter was measured using Walkey-Black method while the particle size distribution was determined by hydrometer method.

Geostatistical Models for Heavy Metal Contamination and Environmental Risk Assessment

The extent of crude oil contamination of the soil samples were determined using metal contamination assessment tools; Contamination Factor (CF), Degree of Contamination (C_d), Pollution Index (PI) and Enrichment Factor (EF). The potential ecological risk assessment tools; Potential Contamination Index (PCI), Potential Ecological Risk Factor (Er^i) and Potential Ecological Risk Index (RI) was used to determine potential ecological risk posed by the concentrations of these metals in Mmahu.

Contamination Factor (CF)

To determine the extent of metal contamination in the crude oil polluted soils of Mmahu, the contamination

factor was used. Tomilinson et al. (1980) posits that contamination factor is expressed thus:

$$CF = C_{\text{metal}} / C_{\text{background}}$$

Where:

C_{metal} is the present metal concentration in the sampled soil.

$C_{\text{background}}$ is the background metal concentration of soil.

The upper continental crust proposed by Rudnick and Gao (2003) was used as the background metal concentration. They include 92 mg kg⁻¹, 47 mg kg⁻¹, 0.09 mg kg⁻¹, 4.8 mg kg⁻¹ and 5.04 mg kg⁻¹ for Cr, Ni, Cd, As and Fe respectively. The CF is interpreted as follows: CF < 1: implies low contamination; 1 ≤ CF < 3: implies moderate contamination; 3 = CF ≤ 6: implies considerable contamination and CF ≥ 6: implies very high contamination.

Degree of Contamination (C_d)

To further determine the extent soils in Mmahu has been polluted by oil production, the degree of contamination proposed by Hakanson (1980) was employed. It is a sedimentological diagnostic tool and is given as:

$$C_d = \sum CF$$

The degree of contamination of an element is computed by summing up the

contamination factors of a particular element in the samples. The interpretation of C_d is given as: C_d < 6 shows low C_d; 6 < C_d < 12 means moderate C_d; 12 < C_d < 24 is considerable C_d while C_d > 24 is high C_d and shows strong anthropogenic pollution.

Pollution Index (PI)

The pollution index, developed by Nemerow (1991) is a soil pollution assessment tool. It uses maximum and average contamination factor values of a metal in its computation. It is interpreted as; PI < 0.7 (unpolluted), 0.7 < PI < 1 (slightly polluted), 1 < PI < 2 (moderately polluted), 2 < PI < 3 (severely polluted) and PI > 3 (heavily polluted). The PI is expressed as:

$$PI = \sqrt{\frac{(Cf_{\text{average}})^2 + (Cf_{\text{max}})^2}{2}}$$

Where: Cf_{average} refers to the average contamination factor value of a given metal while Cf_{max} refers to the maximum contamination value of the same metal.

Enrichment Factor (EF)

The assessment of the impact of anthropogenic effect on elemental enrichment in Mmahu soil within the oil producing area is estimated using the enrichment factor. Enrichment factor

functions by applying a normalized approach wherein any of such elements like Al, Fe and Si may be used as the normalizing element (Seshan et al., 2010). Similarly, Li, Sc, Ti and Zr can also be used as a normalizing element (Reimann and DeCaritat, 2000). Fe will be used as the normalizing element for the computation of the enrichment factor in this study. The anthropogenic sources of Fe are considered insignificant compared to its natural sources (Helz, 1978). Goher (2014) posits that Fe is a conservative tracer that could be used to differentiate between anthropogenic and natural components in soils. Enrichment factor formula is given as:

$$EF = (X_s/Fe_s)_{soil} / (X_b/Fe_b)_{background}$$

Where: X_s refers to the metal being considered from the soil sample and Fe_s refers to the normalizer from the same sample.

X_b refers to the metal being considered from the soil background and Fe_b refers to the normalizer from the same background.

The upper continental crust values proposed by Rudnick and Gao (2003) were used as the background concentration. Results of Enrichment factor is explained as follows: $EF < 2$ is depletion to minimal enrichment and

pollution; $EF 2 - 5$ is moderate enrichment and pollution; $EF 5 - 20$ is significant enrichment and pollution; $EF 20 - 40$ is very high enrichment and pollution while $EF > 40$ is extreme enrichment and pollution.

Potential Contamination Index (PCI)

The potential contamination index used to estimate contamination potential of metals was proposed by Davaulter and Rognerud (2001). It is calculated as:

$$PCI = (\text{Metal}_{\text{sample maximum}}) / (\text{Metal}_{\text{background}})$$

Where: $\text{metal}_{\text{sample maximum}}$ is the maximum concentration of a metal in soil. On the other hand, $\text{metal}_{\text{background}}$ is the background value of the same metal. The upper continental values of Rudnick and Gao (2003) were used as background values. The interpretation is as follows: $PCI < 1$ is low contamination, $1 < PCI < 3$ is moderate contamination and $PCI > 3$ is severe or very severe contamination.

Potential Ecological Risk Factor (Er^i)

To ascertain the extent of the potential ecological risk of an element in the soil sample, the potential ecological risk factor proposed by Hakanson (1980) was used. The formula is given thus:

$$Er^i = Tr^i \times C_f^i$$

Where: Er^i implies the potential ecological risk factor of element (i) while Tr^i refers to the toxic response factor of same element (i). C_i^f refers the contamination factor of element (i). The toxic response factors of As, Cr, Cd, Fe and Ni were given as 10, 2, 30, 1 and 5 respectively (Hakanson,1980). The interpretation of Er^i values is given as follows: $Er^i < 40$ is low potential ecological risk, $40 \leq Er^i < 80$ is moderate potential ecological risk, $80 \leq Er^i < 160$ is considerable potential ecological risk, $160 \leq Er^i < 320$ is high potential ecological risk and $Er^i \geq 320$ is very high potential ecological risk.

Potential Ecological Risk Index (RI)

Hakanson (1980) posits that the ecological index (RI) is a tool used to estimate the ecological risk associated with a metal in soil. The calculation is done by summing up the Er^i and the interpretation is given as: $RI < 150$ is low ecological risk, $150 \leq RI < 300$ is moderate ecological risk, $300 \leq RI < 600$ is considerable ecological risk and $RI \geq 600$ is very high ecological risk. The formula for RI is given thus:

$$RI = \sum Er^i$$

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive Analysis, mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the concentrations As, Ni, Cr, Cd and Fe in crude oil polluted soil samples. One way ANOVA was use to evaluate the variations across the five exploitation sites. Also, correlation matrix used to highlight the inter-element relationships between the soil properties and metals in the study area were computed using Microsoft Excel 2013.

Results and Discussion

The Concentration of As, Ni, Cr, Cd and Fe in Soils within Crude Oil Exploitation Sites in Mmahu.

Studies were carried out on a total of five exploitation sites in Mmahu. The distribution of selected heavy metal concentration in the different crude oil exploitation sites used for this study were represented in Figure 2 using box plots. The boxes compared the distribution of individual metal across sampling sites. This study found that the concentration of Cr across sites 1 - 5, ranged from 7.9 to 13.8 with the highest concentration in site 1. Cd had concentration range of 3.9 to 8.7 while site 2 had the highest concentration. The concentrations of Fe and As in the sites studied lie between 6 and 12 as well as 0.15 to 0.37. Both metals had their

highest concentration in site 4. Ni had a wide range which spanned from 5.07 to 28, with the highest concentration in site 5.

Figure 2 Comparison of concentrations of heavy metals in the soils of exploitation sites of Mmahu.

The Extent Soils within the Crude Oil Exploitation Sites in Mmahu are Contaminated by As, Ni, Cr, Cd and Fe

The extent of contamination of As, Ni, Cr, Cd and Fe in soils within the crude oil exploitation sites in Mmahu were assessed based on the reference values for permissible levels of metals in the soil provided by FAO/WHO (2001). Table 1 shows the comparative standings of the contamination levels at the sampling sites and the required levels in the soil put forth by the Food and

Agricultural Organization/World Health Organization. According to the table, the contamination levels of As, Cr, Ni and Fe at different sampling points and sites within the crude oil exploitation areas in Mmahu indicate that their contamination levels were within FAO/WHO prescribed levels. However, the observed contamination levels of Cd in all the sampling points and sites used for this study were found to be much higher than the recommended values by FAO/WHO (2001).

Table 1 Comparative standings of the heavy metal contamination levels at the sampling sites and the permissible limits in the soil

Sites	Sampling points	As (mg/kg)	Cr(mg/kg)	Cd(mg/kg)	Ni(mg/kg)	Fe(mg/kg)
1	1	0.21	10.40	5.04	17.61	11.20
	2	0.21	9.36	6.21	17.02	7.84
	3	0.21	9.36	5.43	8.80	11.76
	4	0.30	10.92	6.21	23.48	7.28
	5	0.36	10.92	5.82	11.74	7.28
Mean		0.26	10.19	5.74	15.73	9.07
2	1	0.30	9.88	6.59	14.09	10.08
	2	0.24	9.36	5.82	17.61	11.76
	3	0.33	8.84	6.21	23.48	9.52
	4	0.18	8.84	6.98	20.54	7.84
	5	0.21	8.32	5.43	24.06	7.28
Mean		0.25	9.05	6.21	19.95	9.30
	1	0.24	8.84	5.43	5.28	7.28
	2	0.21	9.88	5.82	16.43	6.72
	3	0.18	9.88	4.65	14.67	7.84
	4	0.30	10.40	6.98	22.89	8.40
	5	0.27	11.44	4.65	10.56	8.40
Mean		0.24	10.09	5.51	13.97	7.73
	1	0.30	8.32	4.27	17.61	10.08
	2	0.27	11.96	3.88	24.65	11.76
	3	0.36	11.96	5.04	17.61	10.08
	4	0.36	8.84	8.15	16.43	10.64
	5	0.36	10.92	6.98	19.95	8.96
Mean		0.33	10.40	5.66	19.25	10.30
	1	0.24	10.92	6.59	26.41	7.84
	2	0.21	7.80	5.82	27.58	7.28
	3	0.27	8.84	6.59	25.82	8.40
	4	0.24	13.00	5.82	27.58	7.28
	5	0.33	7.80	4.66	24.65	6.72
Mean		0.26	9.67	5.90	26.41	7.50
WHO/ FAOPLS		20	100	1	50	5000

***WHO/FAOPLS (Food and Agricultural Organization/World Health Organization Permissible Levels in Soil, 2021).

Influence of Soil Properties (pH, OM and particle size) on Metal Concentrations in the Crude Oil Contaminated Soils in Mmahu

Physical and chemical characteristics of soil samples from the exploitation sites are presented in table 2. According to the results of particle size analysis, majority of the samples fall within the sandy loam and loamy sand textural class. % Clay, % Silt and % Total sand varied significantly across the five exploitation sites. They ranged from 7.80 to 11.80 % (clay), 3.80 to 12.20 % (silt) and 76.00 to 85.20 % (Total sand). The highest were from Site 1 (11.80 %), Site 1 (12.20 %) and Site 5 (85.20 %) while the lowest were from Site 3 (7.80 %), Site 4 (3.80 %) and Site 1 (76.00 %) for clay, silt and total sand respectively. Despite the variations the granulometric fractions are not influenced by the presence of crude oil. This is because texture is an inherent soil property that does not alter over time (Brady and Weil, 2008).

The pH ranged between 5.14 and 7.35 with the highest pH from Site 4 and the lowest from Site 1. The pH ranged from slightly acidic to neutral. The higher pH found on some of the exploitation sites in this study might be due to the hydrophobic nature of crude oil, which might induce a potential drought in the surface layers of polluted soil

(Njoku et al., 2009, Wang et al., 2013). Moreover, crude

oil contamination in soil may intensify the accumulation of exchangeable bases like Ca^{2+} or may reduce the exchangeable acidity (Wang et al., 2013 and Osuji et al., 2006), which also supports the increase of pH in crude oil-polluted soil.

Organic matter contents were found to be high in all the soils found in the crude oil exploitation sites. They ranged from 4.85 to 6.05% with the highest from Site 1 and the lowest from Site 5. In the present study, the observed increase in the organic matter content in the soils of the exploitation sites may be attributed to the accumulation of high hydrocarbon content during oil exploitation activities. Wang et al. (2010), in their study, also reported that oil contamination significantly increased the TOC contents, most probably because of the much higher total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) concentration (Wang et al., 2013). Similar findings have been reported by Agbogidi et al. (2007), who concluded that high organic carbon in crude oil-contaminated soil might be due to the slow decomposition rate by soil organisms since contamination of soil with crude oil might have poor aeration.

Table 2 Concentration of Some selected Physicochemical Soil Properties across Exploitation Sites in Mmahu

Sites	Clay	Silt %	Total Sand	pH	Organic matter %
Site 1 ₁	11.00	9.00	80.00	5.10	5.85
Site 1 ₂	11.00	7.00	82.00	4.90	6.19
Site 1 ₃	9.00	17.00	74.00	5.50	5.85
Site 1 ₄	15.00	15.00	70.00	5.00	6.19
Site 1 ₅	13.00	13.00	74.00	5.20	6.19
Mean ± STD	11.80±2.28^a	12.20±4.15^a	76.00±4.90^b	5.14±0.23^c	6.05±0.19^a
Site 2 ₁	11.00	9.00	80.00	5.10	5.99
Site 2 ₂	9.00	9.00	82.00	5.60	5.92
Site 2 ₃	9.00	9.00	82.00	6.00	5.50
Site 2 ₄	7.00	13.00	80.00	5.50	5.50
Site 2 ₅	7.00	13.00	80.00	6.00	5.99
Mean ± STD	8.60±1.67^b	10.60±2.19^a	80.80±1.10^{ab}	5.64±0.38^d	5.78±0.25^{ab}
Site 3 ₁	7.00	5.00	88.00	5.70	5.30
Site 3 ₂	9.00	13.00	78.00	6.10	5.71
Site 3 ₃	9.00	19.00	72.00	5.90	6.61
Site 3 ₄	7.00	11.00	82.00	6.10	6.05
Site 3 ₅	7.00	11.00	72.00	5.40	4.68
Mean ± STD	7.80±1.10^b	11.80±5.02^a	78.40±6.84^b	5.84±0.30^c	5.67±0.73^{ab}
Site 4 ₁	11.00	5.00	84.00	7.00	5.14
Site 4 ₂	11.00	3.00	86.00	7.20	4.90
Site 4 ₃	11.00	3.00	86.00	7.50	5.86
Site 4 ₄	13.00	3.00	84.00	7.50	5.70
Site 4 ₅	11.00	5.00	84.00	7.60	3.94
Mean ± STD	11.40±0.89^a	3.80±1.10^b	84.80±1.10^a	7.35±0.25^a	5.11±0.76^{bc}
Site 5 ₁	9.00	5.00	86.00	7.00	4.26
Site 5 ₂	9.00	7.00	84.00	6.90	5.22
Site 5 ₃	13.00	3.00	84.00	6.90	4.66
Site 5 ₄	9.00	5.00	86.00	6.90	5.54
Site 5 ₅	9.00	5.00	86.00	6.90	4.58
Mean ± STD	9.80±1.79^{ab}	5.00±1.41^b	85.20±1.10^a	6.92±0.04^b	4.85±0.52^c

The Inter-element Relationships among Selected Metals in Crude Polluted Soils within Oil Exploitation Sites in Mmahu.

The inter-element relationships between the soil properties and heavy metals in the five crude oil exploitation sites are presented on Table 3. In Site 1 clay was found to have a strong negative association with TS (-0.54),

pH (-0.55) and Fe (-0.80) but positively with OM (0.72), Cr (0.84), As (0.74) Ni (0.71) and a weak association with Cd (0.57). In Site 2 a strong negative correlation was found on silt (-0.87), Ni (-0.76) and weakly with pH (-0.60). Also in Site 2 a positive and significant association exists, they include clay-Cr (0.89), clay-Fe (0.71) and clay-As (0.78). However,

Site 3; 4 and 5 had positive association with silt (0.76, OM (0.61); Cd (0.76) and Fe (0.78) respectively. The three sites listed above (3; 4 and 5) also had a negative correlation as follows with Fe (-0.56), As (-0.87); Cr (-0.51) and silt (-0.79), TS (-0.61) in sites 3; 4 and 5 respectively.

In Site 1, had strong significant correlation with TS (-0.87) and pH (0.72) while in Site 2 showed a negative and a significant correlation with TS (-0.67), Cr (-0.72), Fe (-0.88) and As (-0.84) and with Ni (0.51) which is the only positive and significant association in Site 2 though weak. Site 3 had a negatively significant association with TS (-0.80) and As (-0.57) and a positive association with OM (0.67). Site 4 had Silt-TS (-0.67) association as the only negative significant association with OM (0.68) and Fe (0.70) as ones with positive associations. Site 5 had a negative association with Fe (-0.62) and a positive association with Ni (0.50), both association due significant but are weakly associated. TS were not significantly correlated with pH and OM across the five sites evaluated but showed significant correlation the heavy metal elements. In Site 1, TS showed negative correlation with Cr (-0.54) and As (-0.62) while in Site 2 and 5, the only significant association each has was on Fe (0.68) and Cr

(0.55) respectively. In Site 3, the significant association were on Cr (-0.70) and on Cd (0.58) while in Site 4 significant association were seen on that with Cr (0.83), Cd (-0.60), Fe (0.55) and on Ni (0.52).

In Site 1, there is a strong negative and significant pH-Ni (-0.80); weak pH-OM-Cd (-0.63; -0.55) and a significantly but weak positive pH-Fe (0.65). Site 2 had strong negative and significant pH-Cr-Cd (-0.86; -0.62) with a significant strong positive pH-Ni (0.94) association. The results of Site 3 and 4 showed a significant and positively correlated pH-OM-Cd-Ni (0.75; 0.70; 0.73) and pH-Cd-As (0.74; 0.85) respectively while Site 5 had only pH-OM (-0.64) association as the only significant association although the association is weak and negative. OM-Cd (0.91) a strong positive and OM-Fe a strong negative significant associations were observed in Site 1 with a weak significant OM-As (0.63) association. In site 2 and 3, a weak significant OM-Cd (-0.56) and OM-Ni (0.56) association was observed which were negative and positive in Site 2 and 3 respectively. In Site 4 no significant correlation was observed between OM and soil properties or with heavy metal elements. Site 5 had only one significant correlation (OM-Ni) (0.71) which is positively strong and significant.

There are variations in the interrelationship between soil properties and heavy metal elements across the five sites imply that there are variations in the soil properties across the five sites evaluated. Also the fact that pH, OM and clay specifically do not control the availability of the heavy metal which is evidence in the correlation matrix, indicate that pH and OM values found across the site were mere induce by the presence of crude oil in the exploitation sites (Wang et al., 2013 and Agbogidi et al., 2007).

Also, Table 4.4 highlights the correlation matrix of heavy metal concentration in exploitation sites in Mmahu. Sources of heavy metals can be defined using iron (Fe) or titanium (Ti) as proxies (Ishiga et al., 1999; Roser, 2000). According to Skilbeck and Cawood (1994), heavy metals that show strong correlations with these two metals mentioned above reflect only natural detrital inputs. This is because in soils, lithogenic metals usually have a linear relationship with Fe or Ti. As such, where no correlation exists between Fe or Ti and any given metal, it implies that either anthropogenic or additional natural processes may have contributed to the observed metal enrichment (Dalai and Ishiga, 2013). In Site 1, there is a negative Fe-Cr-Cd-As-Ni association. However, there is a negatively strong Fe-Cd-As association

while the Fe-Cr-Ni association is negatively weak. Thus, Fe has no influence on the concentration Cr, Cd, As and Ni in Site 1. This implies that the concentration of all the assessed heavy metals in Site 1 are not lithogenic but rather anthropogenic. In Site 2, there is a strong positive Fe-Cr association and weak positive Fe-As association. However, Fe-Ni association was negatively strong while Fe-Cd was negatively weak. Therefore, in Site 2, the concentration of Cr and As was lithogenic based while Ni and Cd concentrations were due to anthropogenic activities. In Site 3, there is a positive Fe-Cr-Cd-As-Ni association. The Fe-Cr-As association was positively strong while Fe-Ni-Cd though positive, but weak. Thus, in Site 3, the concentration of all the studied heavy metals was due to lithogenic events. In Site 4, Fe-Cr-As-Ni had a positive association, though its positive association with Cr is weak. R, The Fe-Cd had a moderately weak positive association. This implies that while Cr, As and Ni concentrations in Site 4 are lithogenic, Cd concentration is anthropogenic. In Site 5, the observed Fe-Cr-Cd-Ni association was positive while Fe-As association was negative. The implication is that the concentration of Cr, Cd and Ni in Site 5 are lithogenic while the concentration of As is anthropogenic. Therefore, the current

concentration of Fe, Cr, Cd, As and Ni in Mmahu is partly geogenic and partly anthropogenic.

Table 3 The relationship between selected soil properties and heavy metals in different exploitation sites (Sites 1 to 5).

	<i>CLAY</i>	<i>SILT</i>	<i>TS</i>	<i>pH</i>	<i>OM</i>	<i>Cr</i>	<i>Cd</i>	<i>Fe</i>	<i>As</i>	<i>Ni</i>
CLAY	1									
SILT	0.08	1								
TS	-0.54	-0.89	1							
pH	-0.55	0.72	-0.35	1						
OM	0.72	-0.18	-0.19	-0.63	1					
Cr	0.84	0.17	-0.54	-0.23	0.36	1				
Cd	0.57	-0.04	-0.23	-0.55	0.91	0.08	1			
Fe	-0.80	0.16	0.23	0.65	-0.99	-0.48	-0.86	1		
As	0.74	0.32	-0.62	-0.06	0.63	0.80	0.38	-0.70	1	
Ni	0.71	-0.29	-0.08	-0.80	0.41	0.44	0.41	-0.45	0.06	1

Site 1

	<i>CLAY</i>	<i>SILT</i>	<i>TS</i>	<i>pH</i>	<i>OM</i>	<i>Cr</i>	<i>Cd</i>	<i>Fe</i>	<i>As</i>	<i>Ni</i>
CLAY	1									
SILT	-0.87	1								
TS	0.22	-0.67	1							
pH	-0.60	0.27	0.39	1						
OM	0.33	-0.12	-0.25	-0.27	1					
Cr	0.89	-0.72	0.08	-0.86	0.30	1				
Cd	0.19	0.00	-0.28	-0.62	-0.56	0.41	1			
Fe	0.71	-0.88	0.68	-0.35	0.23	0.74	-0.05	1		
As	0.78	-0.84	0.48	-0.03	-0.03	0.44	0.00	0.48	1	
Ni	-0.76	0.51	0.13	0.94	-0.43	-0.96	-0.40	-0.62	-0.19	1

Site 2

	<i>CLAY</i>	<i>SILT</i>	<i>TS</i>	<i>pH</i>	<i>OM</i>	<i>Cr</i>	<i>Cd</i>	<i>Fe</i>	<i>As</i>	<i>Ni</i>
CLAY	1									
SILT	0.76	1								
TS	-0.45	-0.80	1							
pH	0.49	0.31	0.24	1						
OM	0.61	0.67	-0.09	0.75	1					
Cr	-0.20	0.29	-0.70	-0.36	-0.35	1				
Cd	-0.26	-0.30	0.58	0.70	0.23	-0.13	1			
Fe	-0.56	0.11	-0.33	-0.36	-0.08	0.68	0.01	1		
As	-0.87	-0.57	0.32	-0.16	-0.46	0.44	0.57	0.61	1	
Ni	0.22	0.47	-0.19	0.73	0.56	0.34	0.66	0.27	0.25	1

Site 3

	<i>CLAY</i>	<i>SILT</i>	<i>TS</i>	<i>pH</i>	<i>OM</i>	<i>Cr</i>	<i>Cd</i>	<i>Fe</i>	<i>As</i>	<i>Ni</i>
CLAY	1									
SILT	-0.41	1								
TS	-0.41	-0.67	1							
pH	0.31	-0.22	-0.04	1						
OM	0.43	-0.68	0.33	-0.09	1					
Cr	-0.51	-0.41	0.83	0.36	-0.14	1				
Cd	0.76	-0.02	-0.60	0.74	-0.04	-0.32	1			
Fe	0.18	-0.70	0.55	-0.45	0.42	0.17	-0.41	1		
As	0.40	0.00	-0.32	0.85	0.13	-0.05	0.79	-0.68	1	
Ni	-0.48	-0.13	0.52	-0.22	-0.49	0.62	-0.52	0.50	-0.70	1

Site 4

	<i>CLAY</i>	<i>SILT</i>	<i>TS</i>	<i>pH</i>	<i>OM</i>	<i>Cr</i>	<i>Cd</i>	<i>Fe</i>	<i>As</i>	<i>Ni</i>
CLAY	1									
SILT	-0.79	1								
TS	-0.61	0.00	1							
pH	-0.25	0.00	0.41	1						
OM	-0.21	0.38	-0.16	-0.64	1					
Cr	-0.21	-0.16	0.55	0.31	0.33	1				
Cd	0.49	-0.35	-0.36	0.49	-0.18	0.35	1			
Fe	0.78	-0.62	-0.48	0.29	-0.30	0.14	0.92	1		
As	0.15	-0.47	0.36	-0.22	-0.44	-0.33	-0.61	-0.32	1	
Ni	-0.26	0.50	-0.22	0.00	0.71	0.49	0.40	0.10	-0.93	1

Site 5

Heavy Metals Pollution in Soils of selected Exploitation Sites in Mmahu Contamination Factor (CF) of Heavy Metals in Soils of selected Exploitation Sites in Mmahu

The contamination factor and degree of contamination of the heavy metals in the exploitation sites in Mmahu is shown in Table 4. The interpretation was based on Tomlinson (1980). The CF of As ranged from 0.044 - 0.075; 0.037-0.069; 0.037-0.056; 0.056-0.075 and 0.044-0.069 with a corresponding degrees of contamination (C_d) of 0.269; 0.262; 0.250; 0.344 and 0.269 respectively for Sites 1-5. The concentration of As across the sites are <

1 and this implies low contamination. The CF and C_d of Cr ranged from 0.102-0.119 ($C_d = 0.554$); 0.090-0.107 ($C_d = 0.492$); 0.096-0.124 ($C_d = 0.548$); 0.090-0.130 ($C_d = 0.565$) and 0.085-0.141 ($C_d = 0.526$) for sites 1-5 accordingly. The CF concentrations of Cr across sampling points in Site 1-5 are < 1 and indicate a low contamination. The CF and C_d of Cd ranged from 56.00-69.00 ($C_d = 319.00$); 60.33-77.56 ($C_d = 344.78$); 51.67-77.56 ($C_d = 305.89$); 43.10-90.50 ($C_d = 314.61$) and 51.72-73.27 ($C_d = 327.54$) respectively for sampling points 1-5. The CF concentrations

of Cd across sampling points in Site 1-5 are ≥ 6 and signifies very high contamination. The CF of Ni ranged from 0.187-0.499; 0.300-0.512; 0.112-0.350; 0.350-0.524 and 0.524-0.587 with a corresponding degrees of contamination (C_d) of 1.673; 2.123; 1.486; 2.048 and 2.810 respectively for Sites 1-5. The CF concentrations of Ni in Sites 1-5 are $1 \leq CF < 3$ and signifies moderate contamination. Lastly, the CF and C_d of Fe ranged from 1.44-2.33 ($C_d = 9.00$); 1.44-2.33 ($C_d = 9.22$); 1.33-1.67 ($C_d = 7.67$); 1.78-2.33 ($C_d = 10.22$) and 1.33-1.67 ($C_d = 7.44$) for sites 1-5 accordingly. The concentration of Fe

across the sites is $1 \leq CF < 3$ and signifies moderate contamination. Based on the calculated values of C_d for As, Cr and Ni which are < 6 , it implies that these heavy metals have low degrees of contamination in exploitation sites studied in Mmahu. The degree of contamination for Fe across sites 1-5 are $6 < Cd < 12$ which means that its degree of contamination in the study area is moderate. The degree of contamination for Cd across sites 1-5 are > 24 and thus, very high in C_d . This shows strong anthropogenic pollution of Ni in exploitation sites in Mmahu.

Table 4 Contamination Factor of Heavy Metals in Soils of Exploitation Sites in Mmahu

Sites	CF _{As}	CF _{Cr}	CF _{Cd}	CF _{Ni}	CF _{Fe}
Site 1 ₁	0.044	0.113	56.00	0.375	2.22
Site 1 ₂	0.044	0.102	69.00	0.362	1.56
Site 1 ₃	0.044	0.102	60.33	0.187	2.33
Site 1 ₄	0.062	0.119	69.00	0.499	1.44
Site 1 ₅	0.075	0.119	64.67	0.250	1.44
C_d	0.269	0.554	319.00	1.673	9.00
Site 2 ₁	0.062	0.107	73.22	0.300	2.00
Site 2 ₂	0.050	0.102	64.67	0.375	2.33
Site 2 ₃	0.069	0.096	69.00	0.499	1.89
Site 2 ₄	0.037	0.096	77.56	0.437	1.56
Site 2 ₅	0.044	0.090	60.33	0.512	1.44
C_d	0.262	0.492	344.78	2.123	9.22
Site 3 ₁	0.050	0.096	60.33	0.112	1.44
Site 3 ₂	0.044	0.107	64.67	0.350	1.33
Site 3 ₃	0.037	0.107	51.67	0.312	1.56
Site 3 ₄	0.062	0.113	77.56	0.487	1.67
Site 3 ₅	0.056	0.124	51.67	0.225	1.67
C_d	0.250	0.548	305.89	1.486	7.67
Site 4 ₁	0.062	0.090	47.41	0.375	2.00
Site 4 ₂	0.056	0.130	43.10	0.524	2.33
Site 4 ₃	0.075	0.130	56.02	0.375	2.00
Site 4 ₄	0.075	0.096	90.50	0.350	2.11
Site 4 ₅	0.075	0.119	77.58	0.425	1.78
C_d	0.344	0.565	314.61	2.048	10.22
Site 5 ₁	0.050	0.119	73.27	0.562	1.56
Site 5 ₂	0.044	0.085	64.64	0.587	1.44
Site 5 ₃	0.056	0.096	73.27	0.549	1.67
Site 5 ₄	0.050	0.141	64.64	0.587	1.44
Site 5 ₅	0.069	0.085	51.72	0.524	1.33
C_d	0.269	0.526	327.54	2.810	7.44

Pollution Index (PI) of Heavy Metals in Soils of selected Exploitation Sites in Mmahu

The PI values obtained from the soils of selected exploitation sites in Mmahu are shown in Table 5. The values were interpreted according to Nemerow (1991). The range of PI values for Cr (0.10-0.12); As (0.06-0.07) and Ni (0.42-0.57) were obtained from sites 1-5. Given that the obtained PI values are < 0.7, it implies that Cr, As and Ni are

unpolluted. Cd in the study area had a pollution index which ranged from 66.45-77.94. This indicates that Cd is heavily polluted in exploitation sites in Mmahu. Based on the PI range of values for Fe (1.58-2.19) as shown in Table 5, the pollution of Fe ranged from moderately polluted to severely polluted. Specifically, Sites 3 and 5 are moderately polluted while Sites 1, 2 and 4 are severely polluted.

Table 5 Pollution Index of Heavy Metals in Soils of selected Exploitation Sites in Mmahu

Sites	PI _{Cr}	Status	PI _{Cd}	Status	PI _{Fe}	Status	PI _{As}	Status	PI _{Ni}	Status
1	0.12	Unpolluted	66.45	Heavily Polluted	2.08	Severely polluted	0.07	Unpolluted	0.42	Unpolluted
2	0.10	Unpolluted	73.38	Heavily Polluted	2.10	Severely polluted	0.06	Unpolluted	0.47	Unpolluted
3	0.12	Unpolluted	69.85	Heavily Polluted	1.60	Moderately polluted	0.06	Unpolluted	0.40	Unpolluted
4	0.12	Unpolluted	77.94	Heavily Polluted	2.19	Severely polluted	0.07	Unpolluted	0.47	Unpolluted
5	0.12	Unpolluted	69.50	Heavily Polluted	1.58	Moderately polluted	0.06	Unpolluted	0.57	Unpolluted

Enrichment Factor (EF) of Heavy Metals in Soils of selected Exploitation Sites in Mmahu

The EF values obtained from the soils of selected exploitation sites in Mmahu are shown in Table 6. The values were interpreted according to Goher et al. (2014). The range of EF values for As in Site 1-5 are: 0.019-0.052 (Average = 0.032); 0.021-0.036 (Average = 0.029); 0.024-0.037 (Average = 0.033); 0.024-0.042 (Average = 0.034) and 0.030-0.050 (Average = 0.036); Cr has EF range of 0.044-0.082 (Average = 0.065); 0.044-0.063 (Average = 0.055); 0.067-0.081 (Average = 0.072); 0.045-0.067 (Average = 0.056) and 0.058-0.098 (Average = 0.071) from sites 1-5. The EF of Cd for sites 1-5 are 25.20-47.77 (Average = 37.59); 27.71-49.86 (Average = 38.50); 31.00-48.50 (Average = 40.20); 18.47-43.54 (Average = 31.34) and 38.79-47.10 (Average = 43.87). Lastly, Ni in sites 1-5 has EF of 0.169-0.346 (Average = 0.200); 0.150-0.354 (Average = 0.242);

0.078-0.292 (Average = 0.194); 0.166-0.239 (Average = 0.201) and 0.330-0.406 (Average = 0.379) respectively. According to EF interpretation by Sutherland (2000), EF < 2 implies depletion to minimal enrichment and pollution. It was found that the average EF values for As, Cr and Ni in the exploitation sites of Mmahu were less than 0.5. This implies that As, Cr and Ni in the study area are depleted, minimally enriched or polluted. Cd values in the study area were found to all fall within EF 20 - 40. This indicates that Cd has very high enrichment and pollution in Mmahu.

Further more, Zhang and Liu (2002) hold that EF values that are within 1.5 are indicative of geogenic enrichment while EF values more than 1.5, are indicative of anthropogenic enrichment. Hence, As, Cr and Ni with EF values lower than 1.5 are geogenic while the enrichment of Cd with EF values more than 1.5 is anthropogenic.

Table 6 Enrichment Factor (EF) of Heavy Metals in Soils of selected Exploitation Sites in Mmahu

Sites	EF_{As}	EF_{Cr}	EF_{Cd}	EF_{Ni}
Site 1 ₁	0.020	0.051	25.20	0.169
Site 1 ₂	0.028	0.065	44.36	0.233
Site 1 ₃	0.019	0.044	25.86	0.080
Site 1 ₄	0.043	0.082	47.77	0.346
Site 1 ₅	0.052	0.082	44.77	0.173
Average	0.032	0.065	37.59	0.200
Site 2 ₁	0.031	0.054	36.61	0.150
Site 2 ₂	0.021	0.044	27.71	0.161
Site 2 ₃	0.036	0.051	36.53	0.264
Site 2 ₄	0.024	0.062	49.86	0.281
Site 2 ₅	0.030	0.063	41.77	0.354
Average	0.029	0.055	38.50	0.242
Site 3 ₁	0.035	0.067	41.77	0.078
Site 3 ₂	0.033	0.081	48.50	0.262
Site 3 ₃	0.024	0.069	33.21	0.201
Site 3 ₄	0.037	0.068	46.53	0.292
Site 3 ₅	0.034	0.075	31.00	0.135
Average	0.033	0.072	40.20	0.194
Site 4 ₁	0.031	0.045	23.71	0.187
Site 4 ₂	0.024	0.056	18.47	0.225
Site 4 ₃	0.037	0.065	28.01	0.187
Site 4 ₄	0.036	0.046	42.87	0.166
Site 4 ₅	0.042	0.067	43.64	0.239
Average	0.034	0.056	31.34	0.201
Site 5 ₁	0.032	0.076	47.10	0.361
Site 5 ₂	0.030	0.059	44.75	0.406
Site 5 ₃	0.034	0.058	43.96	0.330
Site 5 ₄	0.035	0.098	44.75	0.406
Site 5 ₅	0.052	0.064	38.79	0.393
Average	0.036	0.071	43.87	0.379

Potential Contamination Index (PCI) of Heavy Metals in Soils of selected Exploitation Sites in Mmahu

The PCI values obtained from the soils of selected exploitation sites in Mmahu are shown in Table 7. The values were interpreted according to Davaulter and Rognerud (2001). The range of PCI values for Cr (0.11-0.14); As (0.06-0.08) and Ni (0.49-0.59) were obtained from sites 1-5. Given that the obtained PCI

values are < 1, it implies that Cr, As and Ni all have low contamination. Cd and Fe in the study area had a pollution contamination index which ranged from 69.00-90.50 and 1.67-2.33 respectively. This indicates that the contamination of Cd (> 3) is very severe while the contamination of Fe (1 < PCI < 3) is moderate in the exploitation sites in Mmahu.

Table 7 Potential Contamination Index (PCI) of Heavy Metals in Soils of selected Exploitation Sites in Mmahu

Sites	PCI _{Cr}	Status	PCI _{Cd}	Status	PCI _{Fe}	Status	PCI _{As}	Status	PCI _{Ni}	Status
1	0.12	Low	69.00	Very Severe	2.33	Moderate	0.08	Low	0.50	Low
2	0.11	Low	77.56	Very Severe	2.33	Moderate	0.07	Low	0.51	Low
3	0.12	Low	77.56	Very Severe	1.67	Moderate	0.06	Low	0.49	Low
4	0.13	Low	90.50	Very Severe	2.33	Moderate	0.08	Low	0.52	Low
5	0.14	Low	73.27	Very Severe	1.67	Moderate	0.07	Low	0.59	Low

Potential Ecological Risk Factor (Erⁱ) and Potential Ecological Risk Index (RI) of Heavy Metals in Soils of selected Exploitation Sites in Mmahu

The potential ecological risk factor values obtained from the soils of selected exploitation sites in Mmahu are shown in Table 8. The values were interpreted according to Hakanson (1980). The range of Erⁱ values for As in Site 1-5 are: 0.44-0.75 (RI = 2.69); 0.37-0.62 (RI = 2.62); 0.37-0.62 (RI = 2.50); 0.56-0.75 (RI = 3.44) and 0.44-0.69 (RI = 2.69); Cr has Erⁱ range of 0.20-0.24 (RI = 1.11); 0.18-0.21 (RI = 0.98); 0.19-0.25 (RI = 0.10); 0.18-0.26 (RI = 1.13) and 0.17-0.28 (RI = 1.05)

from sites 1-5. The Erⁱ of Cd for sites 1-5 are 1680.00-2070.00 (RI = 9570.00); 1810.00-2326.67 (RI = 1034.33); 1550.00-2326.67 (RI = 9176.69); 1293.00-2715.00 (RI = 9438.33) and 1551.67-2198.00 (RI = 9826.33). Ni in sites 1-5 has Erⁱ of 0.94-2.50 (RI = 8.37); 1.50-2.56 (RI = 10.61); 0.56-2.44 (RI = 7.43); 1.75-2.62 (RI = 10.24) and 2.62-2.93 (RI = 14.05) respectively. Lastly, in sites 1-5, the Erⁱ of Fe are as follows; 1.44-2.33 (RI = 9.00); 1.44-2.33 (RI = 9.22); 1.33-1.67 (RI = 7.67); 1.78-2.33 (RI = 10.22) and 1.33-1.67 (RI = 7.44). Based on the interpretation of Erⁱ and RI by Hakanson

(1980), $Eri < 40$ indicates low potential ecological risk while $RI < 150$ is low ecological risk. This means that the concentrations of As, Cr, Ni and Fe in the exploitation sites in Mmahu pose little or no ecological risk. However, the

Eri concentrations of Cd in different sites in the study area at $Eri \geq 320$ poses a very high potential ecological risk while values of RI recorded across sites were ≥ 600 and a indicates a very high ecological risk in Mmahu.

Table 8 Potential Ecological Risk Factor (Eri) and Potential Ecological Risk Index (RI) of Heavy Metals in Soils of selected Exploitation Sites in Mmahu

Sites	Eri_{As}	Eri_{Cr}	Eri_{Cd}	Eri_{Ni}	Eri_{Fe}
Site 1 ₁	0.44	0.23	1680.00	1.87	2.22
Site 1 ₂	0.44	0.20	2070.00	1.81	1.56
Site 1 ₃	0.44	0.20	1810.00	0.94	2.33
Site 1 ₄	0.62	0.24	2070.00	2.50	1.44
Site 1 ₅	0.75	0.24	1940.00	1.25	1.44
RI	2.69	1.11	9570.00	8.37	9.00
Site 2 ₁	0.62	0.21	2196.67	1.50	2.00
Site 2 ₂	0.50	0.20	1940.00	1.87	2.33
Site 2 ₃	0.69	0.19	2070.00	2.50	1.89
Site 2 ₄	0.37	0.19	2326.67	2.19	1.56
Site 2 ₅	0.44	0.18	1810.00	2.56	1.44
RI	2.62	0.98	10343.33	10.61	9.22
Site 3 ₁	0.50	0.19	1810.00	0.56	1.44
Site 3 ₂	0.44	0.21	1940.00	1.75	1.33
Site 3 ₃	0.37	0.21	1550.00	1.56	1.56
Site 3 ₄	0.62	0.23	2326.67	2.44	1.67
Site 3 ₅	0.56	0.25	1550.00	1.12	1.67
RI	2.50	1.10	9176.67	7.43	7.67
Site 4 ₁	0.62	0.18	1422.33	1.87	2.00
Site 4 ₂	0.56	0.26	1293.00	2.62	2.33
Site 4 ₃	0.75	0.26	1680.67	1.87	2.00
Site 4 ₄	0.75	0.19	2715.00	1.75	2.11
Site 4 ₅	0.75	0.24	2327.33	2.12	1.78
RI	3.44	1.13	9438.33	10.24	10.22
Site 5 ₁	0.50	0.24	2198.00	2.81	1.56
Site 5 ₂	0.44	0.17	1939.33	2.93	1.44
Site 5 ₃	0.56	0.19	2198.00	2.75	1.67
Site 5 ₄	0.50	0.28	1939.33	2.93	1.44
Site 5 ₅	0.69	0.17	1551.67	2.62	1.33
RI	2.69	1.05	9826.33	14.05	7.44

Conclusion

In conclusion, the concentrations of As, Cr, Ni and Fe in soils near crude oil exploitation sites in Mmahu ranged from low to moderate concentrations while Cd concentration is very high. The concentrations of As, Cr, Ni and Fe are largely lithogenic while Cd concentration is mainly anthropogenic. Again, the concentrations of As, Cr, Ni and Fe in the exploitation sites in Mmahu pose little or no ecological risk while the concentration of Cd in different sites in the study area poses a very high potential ecological risk in Mmahu. Based on the foregoing conclusion, remediation of Cd is highly recommended. Cd remediation will save the people who depend directly or indirectly on crops planted within this contaminated area from Cd associated health risk (chronic kidney disease, cancer, osteoporosis, cardiovascular disease and diabetes). Also, high Cd concentration in the soil depletes nutrients in the soil and inhibits seed germination.

References

Agbogidi, O. M., Eruotor, P. G., Akparobi, S. O. and Nnaji, G. U. (2007). Evaluation of crude oil contaminated soil on the mineral nutrient elements of maize (*Zea mays* L.). *Journal of Agronomy*, 6(1):188.

Alozie, M. T. (2020). Niger Delta: young men face exclusion and violence in one of the most polluted places on earth. *The Conversation*, July, 13.

Amobi, F. (2017). N'Delta Communities Lament Oil Spillages, hails Foundation's Intervention. *Punch*, 8th April.

Brady, N. C. and Weils, R. R. (2008). *The nature and properties of soil*, 14 ed. Prentice-Hall Upper Saddle River, New Jersey

Dalai, B. and Ishiga, H. (2013). Identification of Ancient Human Activity Using Multi-element Analysis of Soils at a Medieval Harbor Site in Masuda City, Shimane Prefecture, Japan. *Earth Science (Chikyu Kagaku)*.67:75-86.

Davault, V. and Rognerud, S. (2001). Heavy Metal Pollution in Sediments of the Pasvik River Drainage. *Chemosphere*, 42, 9 - 18.

Defew, L. H., Mair, J. M., and Guzman, H. M. (2005). An assessment of metal contamination in mangrove sediments and leaves from puntamalabay, Pacific Panama. *Maritime. Pollution Bulletin*, 50: 547-552.

Chinedu, E. and Chukwuma, K. C. (2018). Oil Spillage and Heavy Metals Toxicity Risk in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *J. Health Pollut.* 8(19): 180905.

FAO/WHO. (2001). *Codex Alimentarius: Food additives and contaminants (Vol. 1)*. Joint FAO/WHO Food Standards Programme, Codex Alimentarius Commission. FAO, Rome.

Goher, M. E., Farhat, H. I., Abdo, M. H., Salem, S.G., 2014. Metal pollution assessment in the surface sediment

- of Lake Nasser, Egypt. *Egyptian Journal of Aquatic Research*, 40, 213 - 224.
- Hakanson, L. (1980). An Ecological Risk Index for Aquatic Pollution Control: A Sedimentological Approach. *Water Research*, 14, 975 - 1001.
- Helz, G. R. (1978). Trace element inventory for the northern Chesapeake bay with emphasis on the influence of man. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 40(6): 573 - 580.
- Ihiegbulam, E. (2011). Oil Spill Community Demands from Shell. *Daily Champion*, 18th June.
- Ishiga, H., Dozen, K. and Sampei, Y. (1999). Geochemical constraints on marine invasion and provenance change related to the opening of the Japan Sea: An example from the lower Miocene shale in Hoda Section, Shimane Peninsula, SW Japan. *Journal of Asian Earth Sciences*. 17: 443 - 457.
- Kadafa, A. Y. (2012). Environmental Impact of Oil Exploration and Exploitation in the Niger Delta of Nigeria. *Environmental and Earth Sciences*, 12(3), 19-28
- Lu, A. X., Wang, J. H., Qin, X. Y., Wang, K. Y., Han, P., and Zhang, S. Z. (2012). Multivariate and geostatistical analyses of the spatial distribution and origin of heavy metals in the agricultural soils in Shunyi, Beijing, China. *Sci. Total Environ*, 425: 66-74.
- Mallick, S. R., Proshad, R., Islam, M. S., Sayeed, A., Uddin, M., Gao, J., and Zhang, D. (2019). Heavy metals toxicity of surface soils near industrial vicinity: a study on soil contamination in Bangladesh. *Arch. Agricul. Environ. Sci.*, 4(4): 356-368.
- Nemati, K., Bakar, N. K. A., Abas, M. R., and Sobhanzadeh, E. (2011). Speciation of heavy metals by modified BCR sequential extraction procedure in different depths of sediments from Sungai Buloh, Selangor, Malaysia. *Journal of Hazardous Mater*, 192: 402-410.
- Nemerow, N. I., 1991. *Stream, Lake, Estuary and Ocean Pollution*. New York: Van Nostrand Reinhold, p.472.
- Njoku, J. D., Iwuji, M. C., Osuoha, I. L., and Okoro, F. C. (2014). Effects of Oil Spillage on Surface Water Resources in Ohaji and Egbema Areas of Imo State, Southeastern Nigeria. *Journal of Nigerian Environmental Society (JNES)*, 1(1): 88-96.
- Njoku, K., Akinola, M. and Oboh, B. (2009). Phytoremediation of crude oil contaminated soil: The effect of growth of *Glycine max* on the physico-chemistry and crude oil contents of soil. *Nature and Science*. 7(10):79-87.
- Nriagu, J., Udofia, E. A., Ekong, I., and Ebuk, G. (2016). Health Risks Associated with Oil Pollution in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 13(3), 346.
- Nwadiogbu J. O. 1., Ikelle I. I., Onwuka J. C., Ikeh O. A., Nwankwo N. V and Anarado I. L (2024). Assessment of Heavy Metals in a Soil Contaminated by Petroleum Hydrocarbons at Ebudu, Rivers State, Nigeria. *Greener Journal of Environment Management and Public Safety*. Vol. 12(1): 10-15.
- Nwawuike, N., Nwosu, O. U., Amanze, C. T and Ukabiala, M. E. (2023). Ecological Risk Assessment of Crude Oil Impacted Farmland Soils: A Case Study of Ohaji/Egbema in Niger Delta, Nigeria. *African Journal of Environment and Natural Science Research*, 6 (1): 216-230.

- Okoye, E. A., Ezejiolor, A. N., Nwaogazie, I. L., Frazzoli, C., and Orisakwe, O. E. (2022). Heavy metals and arsenic in soil and vegetation of Niger Delta, Nigeria: Ecological risk assessment. *Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering*, 6, 1-8.
- Orisakwe, O. E. (2021). Crude Oil and Public Health Issues in Niger Delta, Nigeria: Much Ado about the Inevitable. *Environmental Research*, 194. Doi:10.1016/j.envre.2021.110725.
- Osuji, L. C., Egbuson, E. J. and Ojinnaka, C. M. (2006). Assessment and treatment of hydrocarbon inundated soils using inorganic nutrient (NPK) supplements. A case study of Eneka oil spillage in Niger Delta, Nigeria. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*. 115(1):265–278.
- Oyinlola, O. and Adebayo, O. (2014). Heavy metal contamination of soil and water in oil-producing areas in Nigeria. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 8(2), 59-66.
- Proshad, R., Kormoker, T., Islam, M.S., and Chandra, K. (2019). Potential health risk of heavy metals via consumption of rice and vegetables grown in the industrial areas of Bangladesh. *Hum. Ecol. Risk Assess*, 26(4): 921-943.
- Reimann, C. and de Caritat, P. (2000). Intrinsic Flaws of Element Enrichment Factors (EFs) in Environmental Geochemistry. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 34(24): 5084-5091.
- Roser, B. P. (2000). Whole-rock geochemical studies of clastic sedimentary suits. *Memoirs of the Geological Society of Japan*. 57: 73-89.
- Rudnick, R. L., and Gao, S. (2003). Composition of the continental crust. In R. L. Rudnick (Ed.), *The Crust* (Vol. 3, pp. 1–64). Elsevier-Pergamon.
- Seshan, B. R. R., Natesan, U. and Deepthi, K. (2010). Geochemical and Statistical Approach for Evaluation of Heavy Metal Pollution in Core Sediments in Southeast Coast of India. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* 7(2); 291-306.
- Skilbeck, C. G. and Cawood, P. A. (1994). Provenance History of a carboniferous gondwana margin forearc basin, New England Fold Belt, Eastern Australia: Modal and geochemical constrains. *Sedimentary Geology*. 93:107 -133.
- Taylor, S. R. and McLennan, S. .M. (1985). *The Continental Crust: Its composition and evolution*. Oxford: Backwell Scientific Publications, 312.
- Tomlinson, D. L., Wilson, J. G., Harris, C. R., and Jeffrey, D. W. (1980). Problems in the assessment of heavy-metal levels in estuaries and the formation of a pollution Index. *Helgolander Meeresuntersuchungen*, 33(1-4): 566-575.
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (2006). *Niger-Delta Human Development Report*. <http://hdr.undp.org/en/reports/national/af rica/nigeria/name,3368,en>
- Wang Y, Feng J, Lin Q, Lyu X, Wang X, Wang G. (2013). Effects of crude oil contamination on soil physical and chemical properties in momoge wetland of China. *Chin. Geogra. Sci.*, 23(6):708–715.

Wang, X. Y., Feng, J. and Zhao, J. M. (2010). Effects of crude oil residuals on soil chemical properties in oil sites, Momoge Wetland, China. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*. 161(1):271–280.

World Health Organization/Food and Agricultural Organization (WHO/FAO). (2001). *Soil testing and plant analysis*,

Bulletin No 38/1 Food and Agricultural Organization, Rome, Italy, p. 712.

Zhang, J. and Liu, C. L. (2002). Riverine Composition and Estuarine Geochemistry of Particulate Metals in China-Weathering Features, Anthropogenic Impact and Chemical Fluxes. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 54(6), 1051 - 1070.